

Abstract

Historical Perspective and Consumption of Aromatic and Medicinal Plants in Portugal.

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Abstract

This paper offers a historical analysis of the use of aromatic and medicinal plants (AMP) in Portugal, exploring their fundamental role in human health since ancient times. The first references to the use of AMP date back to the Celtiberian peoples who, despite not having systematised knowledge about these plants, used them for therapeutic purposes. The Middle Ages, especially within monasteries, was a period of great importance in the preservation and dissemination of the therapeutic use of AMP; religious orders cultivated and prepared the plants systematically.

With Portuguese maritime expansion in the 15th and 16th centuries, contact with new cultures and plants from Africa, India and Brazil diversified the therapeutic repertoire available in Portugal. Highlights include figures such as Garcia de Orta and Gabriel Grisley, whose works were fundamental to advancing knowledge on AMP. In the 18th century, several foreign naturalists carrying out research in our country criticised the underuse of national plant resources.

In the transition to the 20th century, there was growth in the AMP market, with a focus on its recollection and commercialisation, mainly in rural regions, while science began to validate traditional uses. In the 70s and 80s, popular medicine and phytotherapeutic practices began to be more recognised by science; at the end of the 20th century and beginning of the 21st century, AMP cultivation resurfaced with projects such as Cantinho das Aromáticas, which stood out for the organic production and sale of herbal teas and infusions.

In conclusion, AMP continue to play a significant role in health and well-being today. The future of their use depends on a balance between respect for traditions and the development of sustainable agricultural practices, aiming at the preservation of native species and innovation in the natural and organic products market.

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